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USING FITNESS TRACKERS TO MONITOR THE FUNCTIONAL PARAMETERS OF THE BODY

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Annotation: The possibility of prevention of cardiovascular diseases with the help of fitness trackers and the possibility of their use in students has been studied. The following methods were used in the work: an anonymous sociological survey, a comparative evaluation method for collecting, studying and processing the results obtained. As a result of the study, it was found that fitness trackers can be useful for monitoring vital signs, monitoring of which will help reduce the risk of acute complications. Buy fitness bracelets for monitoring the functional parameters of the body.

Keywords: human health, cardiovascular diseases, fitness tracker, students

Relevance. Currently, diseases of the cardiovascular system are in the first place in the structure of morbidity and mortality of the population. According to the World Health Organization (WHO): «About 17 million people die from heart disease every year in the world. According to WHO estimates, by 2030, about 23.6 million people will die from cardiovascular diseases every year» [1–4].

In the modern world, various devices that help people monitor their health have become widespread. Among them are fitness trackers. Tracking indicators such as daily activity, sleep phases, calorie consumption, heart rate is an important preventive measure for the development of pathologies of the cardiovascular system [5–8].

The purpose of the study. To study the possibility of preventing cardiovascular diseases with the help of fitness trackers and the possibility of using them in medical students.

Materials and methods of research. The following methods were used in the work: an anonymous sociological survey, a comparative evaluation method for collecting, studying and processing the results obtained. The respondents were 100 students aged 18 to 22 years (72 % of whom were girls, 28 % were boys). The measurement algorithm includes the following: heart rate monitors built into fitness bracelets measure the heart rate using optical technology. To do this, the device has a special LED, the light flicker of which can be seen when using the bracelet. It shines through the skin reaching the blood vessels. At the moment when the heart contracts, the blood moves intensively through the body. As a result, the vessel abruptly fills up and becomes darker. As soon as the blood driven by the wave is removed, the vessel cavity is almost completely empty and it becomes lighter externally, so the LED glow is observed [4]. The detector built into the bracelet records the cycles of darkening and lightening of blood vessels, which are a reflection of the heart rate.

The results of the study and their discussion. It was found that 27 % of respondents use fitness trackers on a regular basis and regularly monitor the performance of devices; 7 % plan to purchase fitness bracelets; 17 % use bracelets, but not in everyday life; 49 % do not use fitness bracelets. It is shown that 82 % of respondents consider fitness trackers to be a useful device. It was revealed that 72 % of respondents among relatives have people suffering from various pathologies of the cardiovascular system; 3 % do not have accurate data on the presence or absence of these diseases in their relatives; 15 % confirmed that their relatives had not encountered these problems.

It was found that 57 % of respondents are sometimes exposed to stress; 33 % face stress on a regular basis; 10 % almost never experience stress.

It was revealed that 50 % of respondents have problems with sleep (face constant lack of sleep, often sleep less than 8 hours); 17 % suffer from insomnia; 5 % have irregular sleep problems; 18 % always get enough sleep and do not face insomnia.

It is shown that 85 % of respondents are characterized by standard pulse rates in the range of 60-70 beats / min.; 7 % pulse is usually less than 60 beats / min.; 8 % more than 95 beats / min

. It is established that 65 % of respondents regularly take from 5 to 10 thousand steps; 17 % more than 10 thousand.; 18 % less than 5 thousand. Based on the conducted research, it was found that fitness trackers are an actual device, 70 % of respondents recognize their usefulness. It was revealed that 44 % of respondents use fitness bracelets to track indicators.

Thus, students need to reduce stress levels, restore sleep patterns, and increase daily physical activity. It is recommended to undergo an annual examination by a cardiologist. Respondents whose indicators are significantly deviated from the norm need to visit a therapist and undergo an examination.

Fitness trackers carry out the most accurate heart rate measurements, monitor sleep indicators, monitor the level of physical activity, monitor the degree of stress and are convenient and mobile devices, so they can be used in everyday life in almost any conditions. Therefore, the use of fitness bracelets is largely important for the prevention of cardiovascular diseases.

Conclusions. As a result of the study, it was found that fitness trackers can be useful for monitoring vital signs, tracking sleep phases, measuring pulse, calculating stress levels, and monitoring physical activity. All these data significantly affect the cardiovascular system, so their control will help reduce the risk of developing these pathologies. Thus, it is advisable for students to purchase fitness bracelets to monitor the functional indicators of the body.

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